

From Data Model to Interoperable Metadata: Implementing the H2IOSC Resource Description Schema across a Multi-Infrastructure Pipeline

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Abstract. This paper describes the implementation of the H2IOSC resource description schema across a complete metadata pipeline, from user input to OAI-PMH protocol output. The H2IOSC project federates four European research infrastructures (OPERAS, E-RIHS, CLARIN, DARIAH) and requires a unified data model capable of describing heterogeneous scholarly resources – tools, datasets, publications, projects, services, terminology resources, learning resources, and workflows – while preserving infrastructure-specific semantics. We present the data model design, its concrete realization across four system layers (HTML form, JSON storage, native OAI-PMH XML, Dublin Core XML), and the mapping strategies employed at each transformation step. The model supports multilingual metadata, controlled vocabularies, structured identity management with role-based actor associations, and a property system that enforces type-specific constraints. We document the design decisions, the trade-offs between normalization and protocol compliance, and the validation results. The implementation is operational and serves metadata from multiple infrastructures through a validated OAI-PMH 2.0 endpoint.

Keywords: data model, metadata, OAI-PMH, H2IOSC, OPERAS, Dublin Core, research infrastructure, interoperability, FAIR, SSH, multilingual metadata, controlled vocabularies

1. Introduction

Research infrastructures in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) produce and manage a wide variety of digital resources: software tools, curated datasets, scholarly publications, research projects, digital services, terminology resources, learning materials, and computational workflows. Describing these heterogeneous resources within a unified metadata framework, while preserving the specificity required by each infrastructure's disciplinary practices, is necessary for cross-infrastructure interoperability.

The H2IOSC project (Humanities and Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud), funded under the Italian PNRR, addresses this challenge through its Work Package 5 (Marketplace), which provides a unified catalogue for resources contributed by the Italian nodes of OPERAS, E-RIHS, CLARIN, and DARIAH. The data model underpinning this catalogue must satisfy competing requirements: it must be expressive enough to capture the richness of domain-specific resource descriptions, structured enough to enforce data quality, and standardized enough to enable interoperability with external catalogues (EOSC, SSHOC) through protocols such as OAI-PMH 2.0.

While the theoretical foundations of the H2IOSC Common Semantic Framework were developed within Work Package 4, the practical implementation of the data model – its realization as input forms, storage structures, transformation logic, and protocol-compliant output – was carried out within Work Package 5 by OPERAS-IT. This paper documents that implementation, focusing on the design decisions that govern how metadata travels through the system and the trade-offs involved at each transformation step.

The system architecture and OAI-PMH implementation are described in a companion technical note [1]. The orchestration framework that builds upon this metadata layer is described in [2]. The present paper focuses specifically on the data model and its transformations.

2. Data Model Design

2.1 Design Principles

The data model was designed according to four guiding principles:

Multi-type resource support. The model defines eight resource types: tool, dataset, publication, project, service, terminology_resource, learning_resource, and workflow. Each type shares a common core of fields but admits a different set of properties, enforced through type-specific constraints.

Multilingual by default. All textual fields that are user-facing (names, descriptions, property values, identity labels, contact labels) support parallel values in Italian and English, following a MultilingualString pattern.

Separation of concerns. The model separates items (resource descriptions) from their associated metadata: properties, media attachments, identities (persons, organizations, infrastructures), actors (role-based associations between identities and items), contacts, sources (external identifiers), and relations (typed links between items).

Controlled vocabulary integration. Properties that represent categorical values reference external controlled vocabularies (TaDiRAH for activities, ISO 639-3 for languages, SSHOC vocabularies for keywords and resource categories, among others), promoting semantic interoperability.

2.2 Entity Structure

The data model comprises eight entity types organized around the central Item entity:

Item is the primary entity, representing a single catalogued resource. Required fields include: id (system-generated), name (multilingual), type (constrained to the eight allowed values), uri (unique resource identifier), and publicationState (draft or published). Optional fields include: shortDescription and longDescription (multilingual), version, validationDate (for workflows), visible (boolean, controls Marketplace visibility), permissionRequired (boolean, indicates restricted access), and documentationUri (link to external documentation).

Property associates a typed metadata value with an item. Each property has a propertyCode drawn from a controlled set (e.g., keyword, discipline, language, license, website) and a multilingual value. The model enforces type-specific property constraints: for example,

mode_of_use is permitted only for items of type “tool”, while publication_type is restricted to “publication” items.

Media represents multimedia attachments associated with items, with fields for name (multilingual), mimeType, externalUrl, and isCoverImage.

Identity represents a person, organization, or infrastructure. Required fields include id, type (person/organization/infrastructure), and label (multilingual). Optional fields include externalId (e.g., ORCID, ROR).

Actor creates a role-based association between an Identity and an Item. The role field is constrained to: creator, reviewer, curator, contributor, author, provider, contact.

Contact associates communication information (email, URL, phone) with an Identity.

Source associates an external identifier (ORCID, Wikidata, DBLP, LinkedIn, etc.) with an Identity.

Relation creates a typed directional link between two Items (relates_to, mentions, documents, extends, and their inverses).

2.3 Type-Specific Property Constraints

A distinctive feature of the model is the *property-to-type* mapping matrix, which defines which property codes are recommended for each item type. This matrix serves both as a data entry guide (the web application highlights recommended properties based on the selected item type) and as a validation constraint (the harvesting system rejects properties that are not allowed for a given type).

Codice	Tool	Dataset	Publication	Project	Service	Terminology resource	Learning resource	Workflow
<i>Categorisation</i>								
activity	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
keyword	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
discipline	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
language	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
mode_of_use	●							
object_format		●	●			●	●	
extent		●	●			●	●	
intended_audience					●	●	●	
standard						●		●
resource_category	●	●	●	●	●	●		●

Figure 1 - Excerpt from the property-to-type mapping matrix (Categorisation section). Red dots indicate recommended properties for each item type. Properties such as mode_of_use are restricted to a single type (Tool), while activity and keyword apply to all types. The complete matrix includes five additional sections (Context, Access, Bibliographic, Technical) with 25 further property codes, available in the system documentation.

The mapping reflects disciplinary practices: bibliographic properties (publisher, journal, volume, pages) are restricted to publications and datasets; technical properties

(technical_readiness_level) to tools; and workflow-specific properties (manifest, workflow_script, life_cycle_status) to workflows.

3. Four-Layer Implementation

The data model is realized across four distinct system layers, each with its own representation format and design constraints. We trace the complete lifecycle using representative field categories.

H2IOSC METADATA PIPELINE: 4-LAYER TRANSFORMATIONS

Tracing the 'name' field

Figure 2 - Four-Layer Implementation

3.1 Layer 1: HTML Data Entry

The web application presents the data model as a tabbed interface with eight sections (Items, Properties, Media, Identities, Actors, Contacts, Sources, Relations). Each section provides forms for creating, editing, and deleting entities.

Multilingual fields are implemented as paired input elements (one for Italian, one for English). The item type selector dynamically adjusts the recommended properties displayed to the user, guiding data entry according to the type-specific constraints defined in the model.

A key design decision at this layer is the normalization of entities: identities, contacts, and sources are entered independently and then associated with items through the actors tab. This reflects the relational nature of the underlying model but requires users to navigate between tabs to build complete resource descriptions.

Figure 3 - The H2IOSC Data Entry System dashboard

Figure 4 - The property entry form. The grid displays the properties recommended for the specific item type, in accordance with the mapping matrix in Figure 1.

3.2 Layer 2: JSON Storage

When the user submits data, the application serializes it as a single JSON document with a standardized envelope structure:

```

{
  "data": {
    "items": [...],
    "properties": [...],
    "media": [...],
    "identities": [...],
    "actors": [...],
    "contacts": [...],
    "sources": [...],
    "relations": [...]
  },
  "metadata": {
    "infrastructure": "operas",
    "site": "roma",
    "timestamp": "2026-03-04T13:42:04.161Z",
    "version": "4.1-SECURE"
  }
}

```

The JSON layer preserves the normalized structure of the data model: each entity type occupies a separate array, and cross-entity relationships are maintained through identifier references (e.g., actors reference items via `itemId` and identities via `identityId`; contacts reference identities via `identityId`).

The JSON document is stored in a private GitHub repository under a path that encodes the organizational hierarchy: `data/{infrastructure}/{site}/{timestamp}.json`. Each *infrastructure-site* pair maintains exactly one current submission file; previous versions are automatically removed upon new submission but remain accessible through Git history.

3.3 Layer 3: OAI-PMH Native Format (h2iosc)

The OAI-PMH server reads the JSON files and transforms them into XML records conforming to the h2iosc namespace (<http://h2iosc.org/h2iosc/item/>). This transformation involves two fundamental operations:

Denormalization. The normalized JSON structure (eight separate arrays with foreign key references) is reassembled into self-contained, deeply nested XML records. For each item, the server performs join operations: it resolves actor references to identities, and for each identity, it resolves contact and source references. The result is a single XML tree per item that contains all associated metadata.

Restructuring. The flat multilingual fields from the JSON layer (e.g., `nameIT`, `nameEN`) are restructured into the h2iosc multilingual pattern:

```

<h2iosc:name>
  <h2iosc:value h2iosc:language="en">NormaTEI</h2iosc:value>
  <h2iosc:value h2iosc:language="it">NormaTEI</h2iosc:value>
</h2iosc:name>

```

This restructuring ensures that the XML representation is semantically richer than the JSON storage format and can be parsed by the harvesting system independently of the storage layer conventions.

3.4 Layer 4: Dublin Core Mapping

For interoperability with generic OAI-PMH harvesters, the server also provides a Dublin Core (oai_dc) mapping. This mapping necessarily involves information reduction, as the 15 Dublin Core elements cannot capture the full expressiveness of the h2iosc schema. The mapping follows these rules:

- name → dc:title (English version preferred as primary)
- shortDescription → dc:description
- uri, id → dc:identifier
- type → dc:type
- createdAt → dc:date
- Properties with code “keyword” → dc:subject
- Properties with code “language” → dc:language
- Properties with code “license” → dc:rights
- Properties with code “publisher” → dc:publisher
- Actors with role “creator” or “author” → dc:creator (using identity label)
- documentationUri → dc:relation
- permissionRequired (if true) → dc:rights (“Access restricted”)

This mapping strategy prioritizes broad interoperability over completeness. Consumers requiring the full resource description should use the h2iosc metadata prefix.

4. Design Trade-offs and Lessons Learned

4.1 Normalization vs. Protocol Requirements

The most significant design tension in this implementation is between storage normalization and protocol denormalization. The JSON storage layer uses a fully normalized structure (separate arrays with foreign keys), which avoids data duplication and simplifies editing. The OAI-PMH output, however, requires fully denormalized, self-contained records.

This means that the OAI-PMH server must perform join operations at query time for every request. For the current scale (tens to hundreds of records per infrastructure), this is acceptable. For larger catalogues, caching strategies or pre-computed denormalized views would be necessary.

4.2 Multilingual Representation

The choice to represent multilingual values as flat paired fields in JSON (nameIT, nameEN) rather than as arrays of language-tagged objects (as in the formal data model specification) was driven by the simplicity of the data entry interface. This design decision simplifies form handling at the cost of limiting the number of supported languages to two. Extending to additional languages would require modifying the storage format.

4.3 Property Validation

Type-specific property constraints are currently enforced at two points: the web application provides visual guidance (recommended properties per type), and the harvesting system

validates incoming records. Adding server-side validation in the backend API would provide a third enforcement point and prevent invalid data from reaching the storage layer.

5. Conclusions

This paper has documented the implementation of the H2IOSC resource description schema across a complete four-layer metadata pipeline. The key contributions are: (1) a concrete realization of a multi-type, multilingual data model that supports eight resource categories with type-specific property constraints; (2) a detailed account of the transformation strategies at each system layer, from HTML forms through JSON storage to dual-format OAI-PMH output; (3) an analysis of the design trade-offs between storage normalization and protocol compliance.

The implementation is operational and serves metadata from the OPERAS and E-RIHS infrastructures through a validated OAI-PMH 2.0 endpoint. The data model and its transformations provide a reusable reference for projects facing similar challenges in multi-infrastructure metadata management.

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